
**MANAGING BASIC EDUCATION FOR NATIONAL
TRANSFORMATION IN NIGERIA A FRONT-END ANALYSIS**

By

OLUGBENRO, O. A.

&

AKINBODE, O. S.

*Department of Educational Foundations and Management
Federal College of Education, Osiele, Abeokuta.*

Abstract

This paper examines the issue of managing basic education for National transformation in Nigeria. An attempt was made to examine the implementation process of universal basic education as well as its objectives. Efforts were also made to examine Universal Basic education and National transformation as well as some of the problems associated with implementation of Universal Basic Education in Nigeria. It was suggested among others that the issue of funding should be properly looked into, as this will go a long way in achieving the objectives of the programme, which can also be a measure towards achieving national transformation.

Key word. *Managing, Basic Education, National transformation.*

Introduction

As far back as 1948, the United Nations declared that member states should make education free and compulsory, at least at the elementary and primary levels, while serious efforts should be made to increase citizens access to other levels and form of education. As noted by Ogunsanya (2000) the African charter to which Nigeria was a signatory in 1961 at Adis Ababa, reaffirmed the United Nations Organisation declaration and enjoyed its

members to embark on Universal Primary Education, (UPE). Meanwhile, UPE programme was introduced during the second half of the 1950s, precisely in 1955 by the defunct Western Region Government, 1957 by the Eastern Region Government and in 1959 in the North. The UPE was introduced in 1976 by the Federal Government of Nigeria. The other World Initiatives on Education which Nigeria had endorsed include:

- * the 1990 Jomtien Declaration and Framework for Action on Education for All (EFA);
- * the 1991 New Delhi Declaration of the E-9 Countries (i.e nine countries with the largest concentration of illiterates). These are Bangladesh, Brazil, China, Egypt, India, Indonesia, Mexico, Nigeria and Pakistan;
- * the 1992 Ouagadougou Pan African declaration on the education of girls and women;
- * the 1995 Amman re- affirmation of Jomtien Declaration EFA;
- * the 1997 O.A.U. Decade of Education in Africa (1997-2006) with emphasis on Inter- Africa cooperation on education and vigorous pursuit of basic education;
- * the 1998 Durban State of Commitment of promotion of EFA;
- * the 2000 Dakar World Education Forum on EFA which proposed the six EFA goals; and
- * the 2000 World Millennium Summit which articulated the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs).

In the light of the global events on education, the administration of President Olusegun Obasanjo launched the Universal Basic Education (UBE) programme in Nigeria in 1999. Interestingly, apart from the 1955 introduction of free education scheme by Chief Obafemi Awolowo's defunct Action Group (AG), it was Obasanjo's administration as Military Head of State that established the UPE Education Programme in 1976. By launching the UBE,

Federal Government has demonstrated its commitment to the World's agenda on education. UBE is therefore the Nigeria's version of Education for All (EFA) programme.

Scope of the UBE Programme

UBE Programme is a policy reform measure aimed at engendering positive changes in the modus operandi of basic education in Nigeria. It is a policy which intends to ensure that formal education is available to children up to the age of fifteen as well as adult and non formal education. Passage of the bill establishing the UBE was delayed because of the Supreme Court ruling on April 5, 2003 that;

the jurisdiction of the Federal Government with regards to primary education should cease to cover financial through first line charge allocation.

Consequently, the Bills were subsequently passed into law by both Houses of the National Assembly and assented to by Mr. President on the 26th of May, 2004.

The Nature, Features and Objectives of UBE in Nigeria

The Concept of UBE may not be a new idea totally. From all indications the UBE can be regarded as an offshoot of the UPE scheme, which was launched in the country in 1976. As usual with Nigeria, this scheme was abandoned mid-way (Aluede, 2006). The fact that the UPE scheme, i.e., UPE had something to offer perhaps led to the re-introduction of the programme in another name and concept known as Universal Basic Education in 1999. The UBE is a policy reform measure of the Federal Government of Nigeria, aimed at rectifying distortions in the basic education. It is conceived to embrace formal education up to age 15, as well as adult and non-formal education including education of the marginalized groups within the Nigerian

society. The National Policy on Education defines basic education and 3 years of junior secondary school. The policy stipulates that the education shall be free and compulsory. This scheme shall include adult and non-formal educational programmes at primary and junior secondary school levels for both adults and out- of school youths. The UBE has three main components- universal, basic and education. Universal here means that, the programme is for everyone irrespective of tribe, culture or race and class (Aluede, 2006; Eddy and Akpan, 2009). The term basic depicts that is a fundamental or essential thing that must be given or had. It is on this factor that every other thing rest on. Without it, nothing may be achieved. It is the root for acquisition of any knowledge (Eddy and Akpan, 2009). Hence, UBE can be seen as that type of education that every individual must have. It should not be a privilege but a right and it should be the sum total of an individual's experience.

The UBE mission is to serve as a prime energizer of national movement for actualization of the nation's vision working in all stakeholders. This will mobilize the nation's creative energies to ensure that education for all becomes the responsibilities of all Universal Basic Education commission 2005 Annual Report. The Universal Basic Education Commission in its annual in 2005 listed the objectives of the UBE to include:

- * ensuring unfettered access to 9 years of formal basic education;
- * the provision of free, universal basic education for every Nigerian child of school-going age;
- * reducing drastically the incidence of drop out from the formal school system, through improved relevance, quality and efficiency and ensuring the acquisition of appropriate levels of literacy, numeracy, manipulative, communicative and life skills, as well as the ethical, moral and civic values needed for laying a solid foundation for lifelong learning.

In order to achieve the above-mentioned objectives and indeed the vision and mission of the scheme, an Act tagged UBE Act was enacted on the 26th May, 2004. It provides for compulsory, free, Universal Basic Education and other related matters. Following the enactment of the Act, the UBEC was established. The Act provides three sources of funding for the implementation of the UBE, which are Federal Government Grant of not less than 2% of its consolidated revenue fund; funds or contributions in the form of federal guaranteed credits and local or international donor grants. Although, this Act covers both the State and the Local Governments, the state government can only benefit from the Federal Government block grant meant for the implementation of the UBE if it can contribute at least 50% of the total cost of the project. This is to ensure that state's commitment towards the project. This is to ensure the state's commitment towards the project. To ensure that the UVE project enjoys a wide coverage, the Act provides sanctions for parents who fail to send their children and wards to school. Also, in order to ensure that poverty is not a hindrance to schooling, the project provides free textbooks in core subjects as well as abolishing tuition at the primary school and at the junior secondary school levels. The enactment of the UBE Act has a legal implication, which makes it compulsory for provision of universal, free and compulsory 6 years of primary education and the first 3 years of secondary education.

From the various objectives of the UBE stated above, the child should have a continuous, uninterrupted stretch of education for 9 years from primary school to the 3rd year of the junior secondary school. Apart from this, the UBE scheme plans catering for the adults who have been out of school before they acquired the basic skills needed for lifelong learning in form of non-formal programmes. So, the UBE programme is planned in such a way that it shall provide non-formal skills and training for youths who have had the benefit of formal education (Dare and Ihebereme, 2008). The new scheme

has therefore, modified the education system from 6-3-3-4 to 9-3-4. It is expected that there shall be a smooth transition from the primary school (6 years) to the junior secondary school (3 years). This also translates to no entrance examination into the junior secondary school. It is also expected that junior secondary schools shall be autonomous body; not having much to do with the senior secondary school. In order to achieve this, all states of the federation have given the junior schools their autonomy. Thus, the junior secondary schools operate as separate bodies, having their own principals, vice-principals and members of teaching and non-teaching staff.

From the foregoing, it can be seen that the UBE programme in Nigeria has its own unique features. First and foremost, the scheme makes it compulsory for every government in Nigeria to provide free, compulsory and universal basic education for every child of primary and junior secondary school age. Secondly, it enforces all parent to ensure that their children or wards attend and complete their primary education and junior secondary school as stated in section 2 of the Act, which provides some fines for any breach of the Act.

Challenges of Implementing UBE Programme in Nigeria

Although, the UBE scheme started in 1999, it did not take off at the same time in various states of the Federation. The implication of this is that its full assessment may be too early, considering the time it actually took off at the state level. However, as young as the scheme is, some of the challenges it is facing, both at the Federal and state, levels are obvious. The world over, ability to allocate enough funds for a programme remains the greatest challenge that a programme can have. This is also the case with the funding of the UBE in Nigeria.

From the Table 1, it is evident that the Federal Government has not spent up to 15% of its total budget on education in the last 10 years

uninterrupted democracy. The highest allocation so far was in 2008, when it allocated 13%. This pattern of allocation, as mentioned- above, which is below the UNESCO's threshold that is 26% of the total budget is certainly affecting the implantation of government policy on education and in particular the UBE since its inception this position has been well captured by Dike (2001) and Igbuzor (2006), when they observed that the government is in the habit of allocating less money to the education sector and consequently, limits the successful implementation of the programme. It is also instructive to note that the phenomenon of corruption is compounding the problem of shortage of funds in the implementation of the UBE programme. Even, where the allocated fund is not enough, the little that is made available is usually embezzled by corrupt Nigerian officials working in SUBEB offices across the country.

Table 1: Federal government allocation to education sector (1999-2009)

Years	Allocation (billion)	Percentage
1999	23.047	11.20
2000	44.225	8.30
2001	39.885	7.00
2002	100.200	5.09
2003	64.760	11.83
2004	72.220	7.80
2005	92.590	8.30
2006	166.600	8.70
2007	137.480	6.07
2008	210.000	13.00
2009	183.360	-
Total	1.130 trillion	0.00

Source: Olanrewaju and Folorunso (2009)

Another major challenge to successful implementation of the UBE scheme is lack of proper planning on the part of the government (UNESCO, 2000). One of the factors responsible for the improper planning is faulty census exercises. Almost all the census exercise carried out so far in Nigeria, either before independence or after have been marred with irregularities (Oni, 2008). The national population census exercise has always raised political hysteria leading to hyper inflation of census figures, which makes it impossible to know the exact figures for school age population. What this means is that the national population census which is supposed to provide reliable data for planning and implementation has always been politicized with its attendant wrong figures (Dare et al., 2008). The consequences of the foregoing is that just like the present census figures, the previous census data were, also full of imperfection and lapses that they could not be of good use in planning. This shortcoming is particularly visible in 2006 census when the enumerators were reported to be found filling and thumb printing the forms themselves when they realized that they might not be able to cover their areas before the end of the exercise (Anonymous, 2006). The resultant unreliable statistics has led to poor projections. Since, the available data do not allow for proper projections, there is no way that the facilities on ground will be adequate for the number of children in school. This poor projection is a factor that has affected in the University of Primary Education in Nigeria. This problem has been reflected in the provision of structures such as classrooms, laboratories and even quality teachers since 1976, when UPE Scheme was introduced (Oni, 2008), and indeed the situation is the same with the present UBE scheme.

This inadequacy in terms of population data has also affected the provision of instructional materials such as textbooks, laboratory equipment, audiovisual materials, etc., which in themselves constitute another major challenge to successful implementation of the UBE programme. Many of the

schools do not have these materials and where available, they are inadequate and outdated (UNSECO, 2000; Oni, 2008; Dare et al., 2008).

Another challenge of the UBE scheme is the drop-out rate in primary schools considering the aims and objectives of the scheme, which is education for all school age children. The Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) conducted in 2003 revealed that only 60.1% of all the children of primary school age were attending primary school at the survey. In particular, boys had a higher Net Attendance Rate (NAR) of 63.7% as against that of the female, which was 56%. Similar discrepancy is also noticeable in the children's attendance rate in school of the urban areas and the rural areas. In the urban areas, the NAR was 69.5%, while in the rural areas, it was 55.7%. In order to show the drop-out rate, it was revealed by Ogunjinmi et al. (2009) that out of the 42.1 million children below 14 years of age, only 25.8 million representing 61.2% of the total population was in school. At the secondary school level, only 30% of the population that should be in school is in school in Nigeria. Primary school net enrollment between 2000 and 2007 was 63%. The drop out rate for the girl-child is 44%, while that of the boys in secondary school is 39.3% (Olanrewaju and Folorunso, 2009).

From the foregoing, it can be seen that the drop out rate depicts the level of access to education by the Nigerian children, which by implication betrays the universalization of education in Nigeria, many reasons have been adduced for inadequate access to education, which includes costs of schooling (cost of books, equipment, uniform, tuition and examination fees), illness, poverty and economic benefits of education. This then explains why in general terms, any time tuition and all other fees are abolished; there is increase in enrollment in schools. This is not peculiar to Nigeria as Igbuzor (2006) observed that enrolment rate fell by 5% in Malawi, 2 years after fees were introduced into the school system in 1980. Similarly in Tanzania, enrolment sighed by as much as 1.5 million children, when fees were

general terms, any time tuition and all other fees are abolished; there is increase in enrollment in schools. This is not peculiar to Nigeria as Igbuzor (2006) observed that enrolment rate fell by 5% in Malawi, 2 years after fees were introduced into the school system in 1980. Similarly in Tanzania, enrolment sighed by as much as 1.5 million children, when fees were abolished in primary schools in January 2002.

One other reason that could be the cause of drop out is that many children do not start schooling at the right age of 6 years. For instance, only 36.6% of all the 6 year olds were attending primary schools at the time of the demography and health survey in 2003. The implication of this is that the remaining 63.4% is outside of the school system. At 17 years, which is the official graduation age from secondary school, 7.8% of all children were still in primary school. It was also found that 8.7% of the population was still in secondary school at 24 years when they ought to have left school. The delayed entry into the school or education system results into children dropping out of school and entering the labour market with limited qualifications. This invariably makes them live less productive lives. This has led the country into having a less education population, which brings poverty amongst the citizens.

Management Issues in UBE for National Transformation

Though there are challenges in the implementation of the UBE Scheme they are not insurmountable. The solution lies with both the government and the people. To ensure National Transformation through the Universal Basic Education Scheme the following steps should be taken into consideration:

* The parents need to be educated on the need to give their children the basic education for a lifelong education. The government should have the political will to put into effect the Act that stipulates penalties for parents who refuse to send their children or wards to school. Stemming

from this, the government, especially the state and local governments should put in place an educational police force who would go out to arrest children of school age who are not in school during school hours. Any child arrested should have his/her parents charged before the court for contravening section 2 (2) of the UBE Act. The educational police force need to visit the major roads in the cities, mechanic villages, artisan workshops to fish out any child learning a trade but below 16 years of age. These children should be questioned and their parents be invited for interrogation. It is assumed that if education police are put in place at the state and local government levels, the drop out rate shall be reduced to the minimum, if not totally eradicated. To do this, government should popularize this section of the UBE Act through, the nation's media, especially the radio. The enjoyment of government services by parents such as medical services should be made contingent upon the production of a certificate that they have their children in school. In addition, the Homegrown School Feeding Programme, a United Nations' project emanating from the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) of Education for all in the year 2015, being currently practiced in some states, should be extended to other states of the federation in order to further boost the primary school enrolment.

* The issue of funding should be looked into properly. The situation whereby every government claims to be spending a lion share of its budget whereas the reverse is the case should, be addressed. Whatever allocation is given to education the overhead cost, salaries and allowance should not be added to the allocation. Salaries should be treated as a separate component. It is only when this is done that the actual amount allocated to education shall be meaningful. The government expenditure should be closely monitored to prevent

embezzlement by the people charged with responsibility of managing the scheme. With adequate funding, the provision of more schools (primary and secondary) should be of concern to the government.

* Since the provision of more schools automatically translates to provision of more quality teachers, government should make provision and prepare for training of qualified teachers in Nigeria. In this regard, Colleges of Education as well as faculties of education in the Universities should wake up to their responsibilities in giving adequate and qualitative training to the prospective teachers. As much as there is the need to train a lot of teachers to fill the classrooms, quality must be the watchword. Hence, there is also the need to retain the existing teachers to reshape their orientation towards qualitative education in Nigeria. Teachers should also be positively motivated to ensure declaration from the. That is the conditions of service for teachers should be improved to keep them on the job.

* The State Ministries of Education, as the evaluation bodies for the UBE scheme cannot afford to go to sleep because the evaluation and monitoring of the programme lie mainly on them. Therefore, the Ministries in collaboration with the State Universal Basic Education Boards (SUBEB) must be empowered to carry out their responsibilities. Schools should be visited regularly, not to witch hunt, but to ensure that the teachers are performing their jobs as expected of them. The visits should not be sporadic so as to put the teachers and the principals on the alert. The students' records, too, should be evaluated by the ministry. The Ministry's unit on adult and non-formal education must ensure that the various programmes on adult and non-formal education are properly structured and monitored. These programmes should be taken as a very important aspect of the scheme. The UBE's commission's impact must be felt at the state and local government

levels. the SUBEB should also visit schools to ascertain that the resources sent to schools are properly handled.

* Finally, the Nigerian government should endeavour to conduct a national census that will be devoid of political undertone. Proper and accurate data shall enable proper and accurate projection, which will help the education planners and government plan ahead. This will not bring embarrassment such as not having enough teachers, resources for both teachers and students. To get accurate population data, the government should start to think about emphasizing vital registration system by strengthening the present ad hoc vital registration scheme.

Recommendations

In order to facilitate the attainment of National Transformation through the UBE in Nigeria, the following recommendations are provided.

- * All schools should have essential infrastructures.
- * There is the need to establish public confidence in the system. This can be achieved when all stakeholders possess psychological ownership after they would have recognized relevance and desirability.
- * There should be a conducive and child friendly environment for teaching and learning process.
- * There should be adequate number of qualified teachers for the programme and also there is need to intensify the training and retraining of teachers nationwide otherwise the recommended maximum of teacher/pupil ratio of 1:35 may not be achieved.
- * All schools should have essential facilities such as classroom, libraries, laboratories and specialist rooms. Provision should also be made for conveniences such as toilets, boreholes, incinerators, etc.
- * The town/gown relationships should be mutual. Teachers and parents are should be encouraged to attend PTA meetings for cross,

fertilization of ideas and for necessary and timely intervention and assistance.

Parents to be encouraged to monitor the school and outof-school activities of their children.

- * There should be public enlightenment programme on the mass media; the radio, the television and the print about the UBE programme.
- * On the areas of vocational subjects experts should be employed specifically to teach the subjects. Where and when it is possible and desirable, resource persons should be invited to talk, demonstrate and encourage the pupils/ students.
- * There should be periodic assessment of programme particularly in the core subjects-and encouragement of pupils to actively participate in the co-curricula activities.

Conclusion

"Education for all is the responsibility of all". With the present rate of illiteracy which is unacceptable, and Nigeria being one of the E-9, countries, all hands must be on deck to provide at least basic education that will enable the beneficiaries capable of contributing to the national development and of course assist the individuals. No sacrifice should be too much to access, equity and quality schooling for all Nigerian children.

In this regard, it should be put in place ensuring financial policies and legislations that will guarantee steady supply of adequate funds to execute the UBE scheme in particular and education in general.

REFERENCES

- Adesina, S. (ed) (2006): Universal Basic Education in Nigeria: Prospects and Challenges. Imeko: African University Institution.
- Aluede, R.O.A. (2006). Universe Basic education in Nigeria: Matters arising. J. Human Ecol., 20 (2): 97-101. www.krepublishers.com. Aluede JHE-20-2-097-101-2006-1418.
- Anonymous, 2006. The Nigerian Tribune, 28 March.
- Dare, M.O., Ihebereme C. and B.D. Maduwesi (2008). "Management of universal basic education scheme for qualitative education in Nigeria". Reference Publications. Findarticles.com/p/articles/mi-qa3673/is
- Dike, V. (2001). "The state of education in Nigeria and the health of the Nation". www.afbis.com/anaysis/education1020423437.htm.
- Eddy, E.N. & M.E. Akpan (2009). "The prospect of UBE programme in Akwa Ibom State, South-South Nigeria". Int. NGO J 4 (2): 46-49. <http://www.academicjournalsorg/INGO,J//article>.
- Fabunmi, M. (2005). "Historical analysis of educational v policy formulation in Nigeria: Implications for educational planning and policy". Int. J. African and African - American Stud., 4 (2). <https://ojs.siue.edu/ojs/index.php/ijaaas/article/view/69>.
- Fafunwa, A.B. (1991). History of Education in Nigeria. / New EOO. NPS Educational Publishers Limited, Ibadan.
- Igbuzor, O. (2006). "The state of education in Nigeria". Being a keynote address delivered at a round table organised by Civil Society Action Coalition on Education for All (CSACEFA) on 3rd July. <https://www.dawodu.cmp/igbuzor> [Http://www.dawodu.com/igbuzor](http://www.dawodu.com/igbuzor).

- Obasola, K. (2008). "Nine years after UBE, children still hawk during school hours". The Punch of Friday, 24 October. www.punching.com/Article-print2.aspx?theatric.
- Ogbuvbu, E.P. (2007). "Education, poverty and development in Nigeria: The way forward in the 21st century". *I. Soc. Sci.*, 14 (I): 19-24. www.krepublishers.com/.../JSS-14-0-000-000-2007-contents.htm.
- Olanrewaju and Folorunso, (2009). "Ten years of democracy: Nigeria's still education sti wobbling". *Nigerian Compass*, Lagos. www.compassnews.net/.../index.php?...id.
- Ogunjimi, L.O., C.A. Ajibola and L.U. Akah, et al (2009). "Sustenance of Education Sector Reforms in Nigeria through adequate participation by all stakeholders". *Int. NGO J.*, 4 (4): 104-108. [Http://www.academicjournals.or/INGOJ///ogunjimi](http://www.academicjournals.or/INGOJ///ogunjimi).
- Ogunsanya, M. (2000). "The Nigerian Publishing Industry and Universal Basic Education". *He Publishers* Vol. 7, No. 1, Pg. 3-6.
- Oni, J.O. (2008) "University of Primary Education in Nigeria: Trend and Issues". *Int. J. African and African American Stud.*, 7 (1). <https://ojcs.siue.edu.ojs/index.php/ija.q.qs/article/view/104/164>.
- UNESCO (2000). *Nigeria Cooperation for Universal Basic Education*. November 7.